

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Report on **Milestone 7**

SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer 3/3

Dissemination Level	PU
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Actual Achievement Date	29/12/2021 (M36)
Lead Beneficiary/LTP	10. Trust-IT
Work Package	WP2 Communication, Dissemination and Impact
Task	T2.3 SSHOC web presence
Version	V1.0
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Abstract:

The fifth iteration of the SSHOC website went live on 29 December 2021, sshopencloud.eu, and milestone 7 achieved. This fifth release of the SSHOC website aims to raise awareness on the full range of SSHOC tools and services accessible and usable from the SSH Open Marketplace by April 2022. This implementation is focused on an update on the SSHOC results, improved access to SSHOC resources, access to the ESFRI data catalogues and implementation of the SSHOC Trainer's Directory. This document was written in M40, upon the finalisation of the SSHOC project.

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1. Introduction

As defined in the SSHOC workplan, task 2.3 SSHOC web presence will cover all activities related to the design, development, roll-out and continuous update of the SSHOC web presence. An evolved SSHOC web platform will ensure a service-oriented approach to the SSHOC marketplace developed in WP7 and will act as the main project entry point providing a multi-view of the SSH landscape, according to the main research lines of the ERICs involved, namely Art and Humanities, Social Science, Linguistics.

The SSHOC web platform will be conceived and structured to ensure visibility and easy access to the technologies and services resulting from WP3, as well as innovation mechanisms in data production (WP4), use cases (WP5) and training materials (WP6), targeting data producers and data re-users in the SSH disciplines, as well as industry players.

The web platform will also serve as main repository for all published content and allow access to project deliverables and external resources. It will have specific sections dedicated to events and workshops; it may feature sections to collect user feedback and online surveys. It will be able to optionally host any software repository developed within SSHOC and will provide direct access points to the ERICs websites and other relevant websites, existing catalogues and virtual labs. This task will also provide branding for the Marketplace (WP7) and offer support to improve its Graphical User Interface (GUI) and end-user friendliness. Specific branding of the new services will also be provided, making their look & feel homogeneous under the SSHOC umbrella.

In M36, December 2021, the fifth iteration of the SSHOC web platform was achieved (Milestone 7), this document will outline the milestone, its role and the means of verification to its achievement. This document was written in M40, upon the finalisation of the SSHOC project.

2. Description of the Milestone

Via the achievement of Milestone 7, SSHOC prioritises the web platform as a showcase of the continuous marketplace integration with the SSHOC service offer, where direct access to SSHOC tools and services is ensured and available at month 36. An evolved SSHOC web platform ensures a service-oriented approach to the SSHOC marketplace developed in WP7, acting as the main project entry point providing a multi-view of the SSH landscape, according to the main research lines of the ERICs involved, namely Art and Humanities, Social Science, Linguistics.

2.1. Marketplace and Website distinction and alignment

The SSHOC Marketplace provides contextualisation, offers solutions, list of services/tools that can help users answer their research questions. The Marketplace centralises and displays all the tools/services/training materials etc. created and collected under SSHOC WPs.

The SSHOC website will ensure the visibility of the WP efforts. Explain the services/tools and results created under all WPs and highlight their availability under SSHOC Marketplace.

Marketplace page with catalogue of services and tools developed within SSHOC ensures the catalogue uses the same categorisation as the EOSC Portal, services and tools.

FIGURE 1: EOSC PORTAL CATEGORISATION OF TOOLS AND SERVICES

2.2. Methodology

Work Package 2 has formed a web task force of project members connected to coordination, marketplace, technologies, training and dissemination. This team was tasked to:

- Liaise with ALL WPs.
- Create overview & timeline SSHOC results and services.
- Align categorisation.
- Define technical and content improvement on the website.
- Edit existing and new web content.

A spreadsheet on the Project Shared Google drive internal document repository¹ was created to map all SSHOC Services and Tools pulled out over the 40 months of the project, according to their category, type and planning. The spreadsheet gathers all the information defined in the GA, partners were asked to categorise each of these services and tools according to the categories used in the EOSC portal, to map² the type of each service and tool, updated the delivery dates according to the current planning and refine the description of each service and tool.

On the basis of this mapping, the catalogue was rolled out already in MS5, and in the subsequent updates this spreadsheet was used to update the SSHOC catalogue of services. The spreadsheet was also used

¹ SSHOC Consortium internal project document repository in Shared Drive - link to the spreadsheet: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1vZPXOIKbFDyCA1GsUUfavdU00_8rs4wsWzoklxiXyQ/edit#gid=1398076874 [04.03.2020]; access to the repository is restricted to SSHOC Consortium partners; After project finalization, repository will be archived by the project coordinator.

² Blueprint; Commercial solution; Data set / data pool; Demonstrator; Feasibility study; Framework (e.g. software environment, policy document, legal framework); Hardware (e.g. chip, appliance, drone, sensor, system); Infrastructure (e.g. IT infrastructure, transport infrastructure, energy infrastructure, water infrastructure, building etc.); Methodology; Model (e.g. risk model, mathematical model, data model, physical model, business model etc.); Patent (e.g. utility, design patents and plant patents); Policy report; Prototype; Proxy/broker service; Research and/or virtual environment; Scientific publication (Refereed); Scientific publication (Non-refereed); Software (e.g. routine, integrated platform, library, plugins); Standard (e.g. norms, policies); Taxonomy / Ontology; Tool / Toolkit / toolbox; Training (e.g. learning tools, services, modules); White paper or similar publication; Other – please define.

to support the onboarding of the SSHOC tools and services to the SSH Open Marketplace as well as the EOSC Portal. In addition, it provided the basis for the SSHOC exploitation plan.

33 SSHOCing Key Exploitable Results to support your research in SSH and Beyond

FIGURE 2: INFOGRAPHIC SSHOC KEY EXPLOITABLE ASSETS, RESULT OF THE INVENTORY SPREADSHEET, BASIS FOR THE SSHOC EXPLOITATION PLAN

2.3. Enhancements to SSHOC Website

The SSHOC web platform was updated on 29 December 2021, reaching its 5th iteration, with the main aim of raising awareness on the full range of SSHOC tools and services accessible and usable from the SSH Open Marketplace by April 2022, and connecting to user communities. This implementation is focused on an update of the SSHOC results, improved access to SSHOC resources and visibility for the SSHOC user communities through the following upgrades:

1. Connection to the final release of the SSH Open Marketplace.
2. Update of the SSHOC Services and Tools catalogue.
3. Delivery of the online SSHOC Trainers' Directory.
4. Improving access to the SSH ESFRI data catalogues.

2.3.1. Provide access to the SSH Open Marketplace Final Release

The SSHOC project web platform facilitates direct access to the Beta and then Final Release of the SSH Open Marketplace via a dedicated menu item, tailored homepage button and dedicated banner.

The SSH Open Marketplace in its turn, harvests information directly from the SSHOC service catalogue, providing direct access to background information on each of the SSHOC services as described in the following section.

FIGURE 3: SAMPLE OF THE DEDICATED MENU ITEM AND HOMEPAGE BANNER FACILITATING DIRECT ACCESS TO THE BETA RELEASE OF THE SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE

FIGURE 4: SAMPLE OF THE HOMEPAGE DEDICATED AREA OF THE SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE, TAKING VISITORS DIRECTLY TO ITS BETA RELEASE

2.3.2. Update of the SSHOC Services and Tools catalogue

As one of the major upgrades in MS5, the initial [SSHOC Service Catalogue](#)³ has been updated with new information, updated naming and linking of resources such as deliverables, milestones, news and event items to raise awareness on all project outputs delivered for the tools and services and foster further uptake. In addition, a space in each catalogue item has been put in place to link the DOI of the factsheets as foreseen in WP6 and D2.2.

³ SSHOC Service Catalogue: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/service-catalogue> [accessed 09.05.2022].

Virtual Collection Registry

[Home](#) / [Virtual Collection Registry](#)

The **Virtual Collection Registry** (VCR) enables researchers to create, register and manage virtual collections that are integrated, coherent sets of links to distributed resources of interest for the virtual collection creator and user. Each virtual collection comes with a **persistent identifier** and **FAIR** metadata.

The registry can be easily accessed via **federated login**.

The collection metadata is **openly available** and accessible via the **Virtual Language Observatory**.

Property:
Data management

Type:
Software

Accessible at:
[Virtual Collection Registry](#)
[Virtual Collections short guide](#)

Background info:
[D3.8 Implementation report and available SSHOC Switchboard and VCR services](#)

WP:
[WP3: Lifting Technologies and Services into the SSH Cloud](#)

Factsheet:
[Virtual Collection Registry - SSHOC Service Catalogue's Factsheets Series](#)

SSHOC Resources:
[MS5 SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer](#)
[MS12 Implementation plan SSHOC Switchboard and VCR Services](#)
[D3.8 Implementation report and available SSHOC Switchboard and VCR services](#)

SSHOC News:
[SSHOC Workshop Notes: Data Citation in Practice33 SHOCing Key Exploitable Results to support your research in SSH and Beyond](#)

SSHOC Events:
[SSHOC Workshop: Data Citation in PracticeSSHOC Final Conference](#)

FIGURE 5: SAMPLE OF A SSHOC CATALOGUE ENTRY, LINKING THE ACTUAL TOOL DESCRIPTION TO RELATED OUTREACH AND TRAINING RESOURCES AND DELIVERABLES, AND DOI OF THE FACTSHEET ON ZENODO

The factsheet is divided into two main sections: 'Virtual Collection Registry' and 'Access the VCR'.

Virtual Collection Registry

Citing and sharing virtual research data collections

A scientific publication typically includes a bibliography based on persistent references. Ideally any data sets used in the reported research are referred to with persistent references as well. Persistence of references to data has become a topic of growing importance for researchers, as more and more research data are becoming available online for reuse. Furthermore, the need for advanced ways to version, group, and share data - both within and beyond the boundaries of a single research organisation - has become paramount. To meet and support such needs, new concepts and tools have been developed.

A **Virtual Collection (VC)** is a coherent set of links to a set of digital resources (e.g., annotated text, video fragments, interview data, etc.) that can be accessed and cited for future use. The links can originate from different archives, hence the term 'virtual'. The individual resources referred to in a VC may have been generated by different researchers and teams, and usually, they are maintained at the repositories of multiple organisations. For discovery and management purposes, a VC is described by its creator with a set of metadata with preservation of the original access permissions. When a VC is registered in a **Virtual Collection Registry (VCR)**, it is assigned a Persistent Identifier (PID) so that it can be cited and referred to as any other data collection.

The VCR developed in SSHOC will support researchers in arranging and re-using existing resources and collections for new purposes, avoiding the need to create new datasets/corpora for every project.

The VCR was originally created by CLARIN as a service to enable researchers, lecturers, and students to easily collect, group and share virtual collections of language materials and is further developed in SSHOC to also support users working with other data types.

How does the Virtual Collection Registry work?

The Virtual Collection Registry offers researchers user-friendly support for referencing research data that may be heterogeneous and hosted at different repositories. After authentication, users can create and publish VCs that will remain linked to their identity, whereas unauthenticated users can only browse and search published VCs.

The VCR also offers an API for tight integration with, for instance, repository software. Such integration allows users to create and extend VCs directly from the repository user interface and avoids the use of copy and paste when creating VCs.

Access the VCR

Access the VCR directly | Access via the SSH Open Marketplace | Access via the EOSC Portal

QR codes for each access method are provided.

Footer: [in /company/sshoc](https://www.sshopencloud.com/) | [@SSHOpenCloud](https://twitter.com/SSHOpenCloud) | info@sshopencloud.com | sshopencloud.com

FIGURE 6: SAMPLE SSHOC FACTSHEET

2.3.3. Delivery of the online SSHOC Trainer's Directory

WP6 and WP2 collaborated in developing the online SSH Trainers' Directory, a pool of qualified and experienced trainers in the fields of Social Sciences and Humanities that are enthusiastic to bring people that require training to the next level of their expertise in a specific domain.

A trainer listed in the directory can be approached by registering on the SSHOC webpage. Registration was set in place due to the privacy protection rules.

At the time of writing, 17 members of the training community listed themselves on the Trainers' Directory.

Important to note that it was not foreseen in the SSHOC GA, to deliver the Trainer's Directory as an online tool, integrated in the SSHOC project website. WP2 and WP6 agreed that direct access under the project

website was an important step for the exploitation and sustainability of the SSHOC training community. In addition, conversations with the EOSC future project started in M39, who wants to onboard the tool to the EOSC Portal and expand its user base to other domains, ensuring the sustainability of the tools and growth of the directory's user base.

Find the best trainer for your needs!

Trainer Name	Expertise
[Unlabeled]	Biological Anthropology, Social Anthropology and Ethnology
Oleksandr Babych	Communication Sciences, Demography, Economics and Finances
Ricarda Braukmann	Psychology, Sociology
Mareike Buss	Communication Sciences, Management, Social Anthropology and Ethnology
Linus Cepinskas	Political Science
Richard Dennis	Communication Sciences, Economics and Finances, Environmental Studies

FIGURE 7: SSHOC TRAINERS' DIRECTORY

2.3.4. Improving access to ESFRI Data Catalogues

As previously defined in MS6, direct access to the ESS Repository should be ensured via the SSHOC website. With the aim of bringing the data catalogues of all SSH ESFRI landmarks and projects partnering in SSHOC together, WP2 went a step further and provided direct access to all six data catalogues. The image below shows the overview visualisation page.

Data Catalogues

Home / Data Catalogues

<p>VLO – Virtual Language Observatory (CLARIN)</p> <p>CLARIN The Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) provides a means of exploring lang</p>	
<p>European Social Survey</p> <p>ESS The ESS data and documentation section of the ESS website is the access point for all published ESS data and...</p>	
<p>SHARE SURVEY OF HEALTH, AGEING AND RETIREMENT IN EUROPE</p> <p>SHARE The SHARE documentation website contains an overview of all SHARE documentation files provided to the users in order...</p>	

FIGURE 8: OVERVIEW PAGE SSH ESFRI DATA CATALOGUES

3. Role of the Milestone

SSHOC uses various communication channels leveraging project partner networks to produce a set of tailored communication formats targeting different stakeholder groups. The main channels utilised in SSHOC are visualised in the figure below:

FIGURE 9: ELEMENTS DETERMINING AN EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION STRATEGY.

The SSHOC web platform, sshopencloud.eu, is the unique access point for the SSHOC Marketplace and it showcases the project's objectives results partners, news, and events.

3.1. Means of verification

MS7 was achieved on 29 December when the SSHOC web platform reached its 5th iteration, according to foreseen planning. The improvements were visible on the website, showcased with the screenshot images illustrated in section 2.3 of this milestone report. An email was sent to the project coordinator to state the achievement of the milestone, with links to the updates made for verification:

- SSHOC Trainers' Directory: <https://sshopencloud.eu/trainers-directory>
- Data Catalogue: <https://sshopencloud.eu/data-catalogues>
- Homepage: <https://sshopencloud.eu>
- SSHOC services catalogue: <https://sshopencloud.eu/service-catalogue>

4. Conclusions and next steps

Several iterations of the SSHOC website are foreseen during the project's lifetime aligned with the forthcoming results and defined as Milestones 7. In respect to these targets, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The tools and services spreadsheet set the basis for the SSHOC catalogue and is regularly updated as a blueprint for the catalogue, while also serving as a basis for the onboarding of services and tools to the EOSC marketplace in close collaboration with the EOSC Enhance project.
- MS7 consolidated easy access to the vast amount of resources and outputs developed over the course of the project and prepared access for the upcoming outputs and connecting them to the tools and services being developed in the SSHOC project.
- The MS7 brought the ESFRI Data Catalogues to the forefront.

At the time of writing this milestone, the SSHOC project has completed its funding lifecycle. With the aim of showing the project results and outputs for reuse, the website homepage has been revamped putting at the forefront:

- The SSH Open Marketplace.
- The SSHOC tools & services.
- SSH training.
- SSHOC activated communities.
- SSHOC Success Stories.
- SSHOC partner testimonial videos.
- Important deliverables and publications for reuse.

FIGURE 10: SAMPLE OF THE REVAMPED SSHOPENCLOUD.EU HOMEPAGE AT M40, SHOWCASING THE PROJECT RESULTS AND OUTPUTS FOR WIDER UPTAKE